

Rural Amenity–Based: A Veritable Tool to Enhance Extension Agents’ Effectiveness in Delivering Information on Cassava Production to Rural Farmers for Food Security in Delta State

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Abstract

The study was carried out to determine rural amenity-based as a veritable to enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to rural farmers for food security in Delta State. Three purposes and three research questions guided the study. Three hypotheses also guided the study. The work specifically adopted a survey research design. The population of the study was 200 which consisted of 120 extension agents and 80 agricultural education lecturers in tertiary institutions of Delta State. There was no sampling because the whole population was of the manageable size. The questionnaire was face validated by three experts from agricultural Education Department, federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, Delta State. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire tagged “veritable tool to enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to rural farmers questionnaire” (VTEEAEDICPRFQ) consisting of 27 items was developed from the literature and used as the instrument for data collection. The scale for questionnaire was: Strongly Agreed (SA)-4, Agreed (A)-3, Disagreed (D)-2, Strongly Disagreed (SD)-1. 200 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents but 193 copies were returned which was at 97% return rate. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviations to answer the research questions while the hypothesis was tested using t-test, at a confidence level of 0.05 significant. The result of analysis showed that electronic audio-visual aids using electricity, provision of accommodation in the rural areas and construction of good road network can enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information to rural farmers on cassava production for food security in Delta State. The result of t-test showed that there were no significant differences in mean responses of extension agents and lecturers ($p>0.05$). Based on the result of the study, it is recommended that Delta State government should provide amenities in the rural areas such as good road network, electricity and comfortable accommodation to the rural areas to enhance extension agents’ effectiveness.

Keywords: Rural Amenity, enhanced, effectiveness, delivering information, rural farmers, cassava, production and food security.

Introduction

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) is a major food and industrial crop in the tropical and sub-tropical Africa. It is a major food in Nigeria particularly, Delta State. According to Okeme, Ambrose & Bishie-Unung(2020), cassava is a drought tolerant, famine reserve crop and can withstand extended period of drought and some varieties can survive on annual rainfall of only 200mm if suitably distributed. The Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) (2018) affirmed that cassava plays a significant role in household food security, especially in the rural communities. It is usually a subsistence crop grown for food and only the surplus is sold to generate income. Cassava production as used in this study entails all processes geared towards making sure that farmers obtain innovative information on cassava production to ensure food security.

Food security simple means an assurance and an access to sufficient quantities and quality of food in the right proportion for all, including the poor (Ayansina and Adeogun, 2017). Food security is achieved when the people in all States of Nigeria have access to sufficient safe and nutritious food to meet the dietary needs and food preference for an active and healthy life (Egbe, Ojemuyide, Eze and Nwokoye 2022).

Delta State as one of the States in Nigeria has large land and fertile soil for cultivation of various crops and rearing of animals, rich in minerals and other materials required to obtain food security. (Akpomedaye, 2019). Meanwhile, there is still hunger and starvation in the State. A State like Delta can only be said to be equipped and developed when it has food security. (Chukaire, Emerhirhi, Anyoha and Onoh 2018). According to the authors it implies that, there is food security when a country or a State has adequate food supply to meet the minimal needs of its populace without depending on food imports and aids. (Egbe, et al 2022), observed that all the various government programmes aimed at developing agriculture in Nigeria have not yet yielded the desired result because the farmers are still using traditional – based methods. As such, the farmers practice only subsistence agriculture that cannot achieve food security. In the opinion of (Agholor, 2016), the reason why the farmers are still using traditional based approach is lack of knowledge on innovative ideas to apply modern techniques in commercial agriculture. In submission of (Adesiji, Akionsorta and Omokore, 2010), farmers need timely agricultural information from the extension services.

Agricultural extension service is an out of school program in which extension agent is made to work with rural farmers to assist them change their knowledge, skill and farming activities (FAO, 2019). Extension implies informing, teaching and advising farmers on new and improved technologies and getting feedback from farmers to research stations (Imoloame and Olanrewaju, 2014). This is done with a view to helping the farmers improve their productivity, earn more income and improve their standard of living. The main role of agricultural extension is to build capacity of the farmers, change their mind set and help them to make informed decisions for better use of extension services. In submission of Williams (2005) and Asiabak, (2002) if extension agents would be committed in rendering extension services by transmitting the result of research institute to farmers, there must be an effective communication between research institutes, the extension agents and the farmers.

Extension Services in this study are agricultural packages needed by rural farmers in the form of education, farm input, new technologies, and technical advice and information services. The agricultural information gets to farmers through extension agents.

Agricultural extension agents are the trained persons in extension education who are made to spread agricultural information to rural farmers (Okeowo, 2015). Okeowo, stated further that extension agents

train farmers, provide advisory services and information to farmers, also help them form organization for sustainable food production and marketing, as well as teaching rural farmers on improved cultivation, rearing of animals and processing of crops. Furthermore, Imoloame and Olarewaju (2014) stated that extension agents help to collect basic information relating to rural agricultural programmes, supervise beneficiaries on agricultural loans, change rural farmers' attitude relating to agricultural production, raise the standard of rural farmers, identify appropriate marketing channels for the farmers to sale their agricultural products as well as teaching farmers land management techniques which improves land fertility and productivity. They are also the go-between the farmers and the government/research station; sending information from the research stations to farmers and getting feedback on farmers' problems to the government. In this study, extension agents are trained officers who teach the rural farmers to acquire knowledge and skills on agricultural production. They are agents working under the ministry of agriculture either at the state or federal level and Agricultural Development Program (ADP). Mgbenka and Mbah (2018) described extension agent as a trained employee who develops and delivers educational programs to assist rural farmers in economic and community development, leadership, agriculture and environment.

However, roles of extension agents are not making waves in farmers' production because they are not effective in the delivery of agricultural information to farmers. Effectiveness in this work means the capability of producing a desired result in agricultural production by the farmers. Effectiveness in information delivery occurred when extension agents disseminate to the rural farmers the research messages from research institutes and these are applied adequately by the rural farmers to increase agricultural production (Olayemi and Taiy, 2020).

The rural farmers in this study are small holder farmers who carry out agricultural activities in the villages and are in need of agricultural information from extension agents.

The Nigerian agricultural extension service is bedeviled by several problems as identified by Imoloame and Olarewaju (2014) such as inadequate funding, poor logistic support, and poorly trained personnel at local level, ineffective agricultural research extension linkages, and insufficient agricultural technologies for farmers and disproportionate number of extension agents to farm family ratio. Other observed problems stated by Asikadi, (2010) are poor input supply, lack of clientele participation in program development, irregular policy and program instability. In fact, these problems affect the competencies of extension workers and the management structure of the extension program. Asikadi, (2010) further attested that to address the above problems, some veritable tools have to be employed such as provision of rural amenity-based to keep the rural areas comfortable for the rural farmers.

Rural amenity-based are facilities provided that focused on developing the rural areas where the extension agents are sent to work with the farmers. In submission of Ndem, Okafor, Ochienu, Azuku, Nwovu, Edu and Opara, (2020), rural amenities are desirable facilities that are provided in the rural areas to make life comfortable and lively. Ndem et al identified some of the rural amenities as; recreational centers, health care services, portable water, civic centers, reliable security network, good road network, comfortable accommodation, sound vehicles, modern markets, standard schools at affordable prices for the children, rural electrification, WIFI for internet connections, computers/laptops, community radio stations among others. Ndem, et al (2020) added that those rural amenities are necessary in enhancing extension agents' effectiveness.

To enhance, means to improve and increase the quality or effectiveness of a program or a person (Obaniyi & Adewole, 2014). Therefore, to enhance is explained in this work as the use of certain tools to increase the efficiency and the effectiveness of extension workers in delivering of information to the rural

farmers. Oluwasusi and Akanni (2021) said that an enhanced extension information delivery program brings out its worth or goodness in terms of functional contents, effective methods, needed facilities and resource personnel. Oluwasusi, et al (2021) added also that extension agents in Delta State need to be enhanced with comfortable accommodation; to make their work easy and timely in delivering information that would increase farm productivity, marketing link to make good sales of the produce, and to access loans.

Also, electrification of the rural areas; to enable the extension agents charge their phones, laptops/tablets and so on. Provision of good road network; to enable the extension agents access the farms easily for demonstration Rural farmers in Delta State ought to supply enough food for the people because of the various government agricultural intervention programs such as subsidy on farm inputs, loan facilities to farmers and regular supply of improved crop varieties. In support of the above, Ndem, et al (2020) opined that no extension agent would relax to work effectively in the rural area without a comfortable accommodation.

As it stands, most rural farmers in Delta State still operate at subsistence level with low input and low return from their farms because of dearth in information (Egbe, et al 2022). This signifies that there is a gap between government research stations and rural farmers. This gap could be filled by extension agents, who are the go-between the farmers and the research information institutes. It is against this background that this work was carried out to determine rural amenity-based; a veritable tool to enhance extension agents' effectiveness for food security in Delta State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to determine rural amenity-based as a veritable tool to enhance extension agents' effectiveness for food security in Delta State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the provision of electricity in the rural areas to enhance extension agents' effectiveness in using electronic audio-visual aids in delivering information on cassava production to rural farmers.
2. Determine the provision of accommodation to enhance extension agents' effectiveness for timely delivery of agricultural information to rural farmers on cassava production.
3. Determine the provision of good road network to enhance extension agents' effectiveness in assisting the rural farmers in marketing of cassava products.

Research Questions

Based on the specific objectives of the study, the following research questions were developed and answered:

1. What are the electronic audio-visual aids using electricity that enhance extension agents' effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to rural farmers?
2. What are the ways provision of accommodation enhances extension agents' effectiveness for timely delivery of information on cassava production to rural farmers?
3. What are the ways provisions of good road network enhances extension agents' effectiveness delivering information that can assist the rural farmers in marketing agricultural product?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant.

Received: 2 May 2024

Revised: 17 May 2024

Accepted: 27 May 2024

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- HO1: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and extension agents in provision of sophisticated audio-visual using electricity in the rural areas to enhance extension agents' effectiveness
- HO2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of extension agents and lecturers in provision of good road network in the rural areas to enhance the extension agents' effectiveness
- HO3: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of extension agents and lecturers in provision of comfortable accommodation in the rural areas to enhance extension agents' effectiveness.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Delta State. Delta was chosen for the study because it is an agrarian State, dominated with rural farmers who are in need of agricultural information. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study was carried out in three senatorial zones in Delta State. The population of the study was 200 comprised of 120 extension agents and 80 agricultural education lecturers in Delta State. The entire population was studied since the population was manageable. Hence, there was no need for any sampling technique.

A questionnaire tagged 'veritable tool to enhance extension agents' effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to rural farmers questionnaire' (VTEEAEDICPRFQ) consisting of 27 items was developed from the literature and used as the instrument for data collection. The scale for questionnaire was: Strongly Agreed (SA)-4, Agreed (A)-3, Disagreed (D)-2, Strongly Disagreed (SD)-1. The questionnaire was face validated by three experts from agricultural Education Department, federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, Delta State. The questionnaire was administered to 200 respondents and collected with the help of three research assistants. There was 97% return rate which equated to 193 respondents. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire which yielded a coefficient of 0.77. Mean and Standard deviation was used to answer research questions while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The cutoff point of 2.50 was applied in decision making for the research questions thus; any item with a mean value of 2.50 and above was agreed as a veritable tool for enhancing extension agents' effectiveness while any item value less than 2.50 was rejected as a veritable tool for enhancing extension agents' effectiveness. T-test was used to test the hypotheses of the study at 0.05 level of significant. If the calculated t-value was greater than the critical (table) value, the null hypothesis is rejected; while the one with the calculated t-value less than the critical value was accepted.

Results

Research question 1

What are the electronic audio-visual aids using electricity that can enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering cassava production information to farmers for food security in Delta State?

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of extension agents and lectures on how electronic audio-visual aids using electricity can enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering cassava production information to farmers for food security in Delta State.

Table 1: Mean responses of extension agents and lectures on how electronic audio-visual aids using electricity can enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering cassava production information to farmers for food security in Delta State.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	MEAN	S.D	SIG	RANK
1	Charging phones to stay connected in delivering information in delivering information to rural farmers	3.50	0.44	0.21	Agreed NS
2	Charging of Laptops computer in making graphic work with the production of images in educating the rural farmers	3.55	0.67	0.49	Agreed NS
3	Desktop for connecting to internet in searching relevant agricultural information	3.67	0.68	0.75	Agreed NS
4	Ipad/Tablets for getting handy information and making some designs	3.56	0.65	0.83	Agreed NS
5	Electricity helps the extension agents to use power point in making presentations to the rural farmers.	3.64	0.54	0.15	Agreed NS
6	Electricity helps the extension agents in using television to show some agricultural activities that can facilitate the learning of the rural farmers.	3.68	0.59	0.08	Agreed NS
7	Radio for organizing programmes that can reach out to large number of farmers at a time	3.81	0.43	0,60	Agreed NS
8	Electricity helps the extension agents to plug the digital camera to show pictures and videos that can enhance the understanding of the rural farmers during training	3.65	0.47	0.92	Agreed NS
9	Use electronics to monitor and evaluate farmers using mobile apps	2.10	0.49	0.52	Disagreed NS
Grand mean		3.46	0.13		Agreed

SD = Standard deviation, NS Not significant

As shown in Table 1 above the mean responses range from 2.10 for item 9 to 3.81 for item 7. The respondents agreed to items 1 to 8 but disagreed with item 9. This implies that all the electronic audio-visual aids using electricity listed above except electronics using mobile app can enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to farmers for food security in Delta State.

Research Question 2

What are the ways provision of accommodation in the rural areas enhances extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production for food security?

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between extension agents’ and lectures’ mean responses on the ways provision of accommodation in the rural areas enhances extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production for food security.

Table 2: Mean responses of respondents on the ways provision of accommodation in the rural areas enhances extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production for food security.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	MEAN	SD	SIG	RANK
1	Increase in farm production and income	3.66	0.79	0.51	Agreed NS
2	Timely information in guiding farmers on marketing strategies of cassava product	3.83	1.00	0.46	Agreed NS
3	Timely information on climate change	3.51	0.65	0.59	Agreed NS
4	Timely information on new innovations	3.54	0.66	0.38	Agreed NS
5	Drawing a plan for cassava production	3.50	0.67	0.66	Agreed NS
6	Keeping records of activities in the cassava farm	3.81	0.99	0.53	Agreed NS
7	Expand cassava production enterprise based on farm progress	3.68	0.81	0.85	Agreed NS
8	Organizing workshops and seminars regularly to the farmers	3.66	0.77	0.48	Agreed NS
9	Timely information on how and where to access loans and grants that will help to farmers to expand the farm.	3.59	0.73	0.69	Agreed NS
10	Visiting of the farmers’ farm regularly for Ddemonstrations of some new methods of farming.	3.59	0.74	0.87	Agreed NS
Grand mean		3.64	0.11		Agreed

SD = standard deviation, NS = Not significant

As shown in Table 2 above the mean responses of the respondents for items 1 to 10 are above 2.50 the cutoff point. This shows that the respondents agreed that all the items on ways provision of accommodation in the rural areas can enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production for food security.

Research Question 3

What are the ways construction of good road network in the rural areas enhances extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to the rural farmers?

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of extension agents and lectures on the ways construction of good road network in the rural areas enhances extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to the rural farmers.

Table 3: Mean responses of respondents on the ways on the ways construction of good road network in the rural areas enhances extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to the rural farmers.

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	Mean	SD	Sig	Rank
1	Quick access to farm inputs	3.54	0.59	0.41	Agreed NS
2	Increase in the total area cultivated by the cassava farmers	3.56	0.53	0.82	Agreed NS
3	Creating an enabling environment to promote agricultural production and alleviates poverty	3.67	0.65	0.53	Agreed NS
4	Facilitation of technology transfer and adoption of best practices in planting cassava.	3.81	0.57	0.69	Agreed NS
5	Increasing the quick access to demonstration farms scattered around the community.	3.65	0.78	0.32	Agreed NS
6	Increase in the number of demonstration plots that where they teach the rural farmers new innovations.	3.68	0.81	0.09	Agreed NS
7	Facilitating the mobilization of the community to address common problems regarding the outbreak of pests and diseases.	2,40	0.79	0.50	Disagreed NS
8	Increase in the number of extension services which facilitate the introduction of more efficient cassava farming system.	3.66	0.76	0.49	Agreed NS
Grand mean		3.50	0.08		Agreed

S.D = Standard deviation, NS = Not significant

As shown in Table 3 above, the mean responses range from 2.40 for item 7 to 3.81 for item 4. The respondents agreed to items 1 to 6 and 8 but disagreed with item 7. The grand mean of 3.50 indicates that construction of good road network in the rural areas can enhance extension agents’ effectiveness in delivering information on cassava production to the rural farmers.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study showed that extension agents and agricultural education lecturers in Delta State rated all the items in research question 1 above the cut-off point of 2.50. This is an indication that the respondents agreed that charging phones and laptops, using desktop to connect to internet, Ipad/Tablets for getting handy information and making some designs, Electricity helps the extension agents to use power point in making presentations to the rural farmers. Electricity helps the extension agents in using television to show some agricultural activities that can facilitate the learning of the rural farmers, radio for organizing programmes that can reach out to large number of farmers at a time, use electronics to monitor and evaluate farmers using mobile apps. The result agrees with Mgbenka and Mbah, (2018) who identified that rural electrification enhances the effectiveness of extension agents in delivering timely information on cassava production to rural farmers.

The result of the research question two revealed that there were positive responses in all the 10 items by the respondents. This means that of all the respondents agreed that provision of accommodation in the

rural areas lead to increase in farm production and income, passing information timely to farmers on marketing strategies of cassava product, how to access loans and grants, climate change and new innovations; drawing a plan for cassava production, expansion of cassava production enterprise based on farm progress; regular visit to farmers' farms and organization of seminars and workshops and demonstrations of some new methods of farming. The result is in consonance with the report of Oluwasusi and Akanni (2021) who stated that the extension agents in Delta State need to be enhanced with comfortable accommodation; to make their work easy and timely in delivering information that would increase farm productivity, marketing link to make good sales of the produce, and to access loans.

The result of research question 3 revealed that all the 8 items except item 7 can enhance extension agents' effectiveness in delivering information to rural farmers on cassava production. The implication is that the respondents agreed that Quick access to farm inputs, Increase in the total area cultivated by the cassava farmers, Creating an enabling environment to promote agricultural production and alleviates poverty, Facilitation of technology transfer and adoption of best practices in planting cassava, Increasing the quick access to demonstration farms scattered around the community, Increase in the number of demonstration plots that where they teach the rural farmers new innovations, and increase in the number of extension services which facilitate the introduction of more efficient cassava farming system. The result is in agreement with Ndem, Okafor, Ochijenu, Azuku, Nwovu, Edu and Opara, (2020), who reported that construction of good road network in the rural areas is one of the rural amenities lead to quick delivery of agricultural information and multiple demonstration plots by extension agents.

Conclusion

There is dearth of agricultural information to rural farmers in Delta State. It was discovered in this study that all the veritable tools if provided could enhance extension agents' effectiveness in closing the gap in information delivery to rural farmers. From the findings it was concluded that charging phones to stay connected in delivering information to rural farmers, radio for organizing programmes that can reach out to large number of farmers at a time, regular visit to farmers' farms and organization of seminars and workshops and demonstrations of some new methods of farming, expansion of cassava production enterprise based on farm progress, facilitating the mobilization of the community to address common problems regarding the outbreak of pests and diseases and increase in the number of extension services which facilitate the introduction of more efficient cassava farming system and creating an enabling environment to promote agricultural production and alleviates poverty. Certainly, the effectiveness of extension agents in information delivery to rural farmers, will lead to substantial increase in cassava production and ensure food security.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Delta State government should provide electricity to all rural areas to make the place lively.
2. Delta State government, the elites and non-governmental organizations should liaise to provide modern and enough accommodations to extension agents at the rural areas to keep them comfortable
3. Delta State government should among other projects construct good road network at the rural areas to enhance extension agents in quick innovative information to rural farmers.

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